

USING THE SINGAPORE EDUCATIONAL APPROACH IN TEACHING NATURAL SCIENCES

Sh.G. Khaitova

Navoi State University, Faculty of Exact Sciences

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15243037>

Abstract. *This article presents ideas about the use of the Singapore educational approach in the process of teaching physics and astronomy. The use of computer technologies in teaching, modern teaching methods and their importance in student learning are given. Also, the issues of forming students' independent worldviews and teaching critical thinking are discussed.*

Keywords: *the role of the teacher, Singapore education, worldview, critical thinking, Information technologies, constructive approach, methods, mathematical approach, scientific approach.*

Introduction. The most urgent issue of organizing the educational process in general secondary schools is the connection of science and technology development, engineering, natural sciences and everyday life in the process of teaching subjects.

The importance of natural sciences (chemistry, biology, physics, geography and natural sciences) is determined by their role in the development of science and technology, in production sectors and everyday life. Teaching natural sciences in general secondary schools is aimed at further forming and developing the ability of students to apply knowledge in practice by generalizing their life ideas and practical activities.

Today, in order to increase the effectiveness of natural sciences, we need to abandon the theoretical approach to teaching and the approach based on providing students with ready-made educational materials, and focus on developing and developing the student's ability to apply natural science knowledge in everyday life, and on demonstrating and activating students' independent thinking skills.

In Singapore, the system includes six years of primary school, then 4-6 years of secondary school, and up to 1-3 years of post-secondary education.

In Singaporean schools, chemistry, biology, and physics from the natural sciences category are taught as separate subjects starting from the 10th year of education.

In this education system, the science curriculum is based on the spirit and practice of scientific inquiry and identifies three integral areas that are essential to the practice of science: knowledge, understanding and application; skills and processes; and values and relationships. The Singapore Curriculum enables students to understand that the pursuit of science is meaningful and rewarding, as it is based on basic knowledge, problems and questions related to the role of science in everyday life, society and the environment.

Process skills are an important part of science practice within the 2019 Singapore Science Curriculum. There are various process skills such as visualizing, comparing, classifying and others. This curriculum has been revised to cover the direction of science education in Singapore to provide students with a strong foundation in science for life, learning, citizenship and work.

Methodology. Based on the Science Curriculum the vision of science education in Singapore, expressed in the three “INs” – Inspire, Inquire and Innovate, can be achieved by developing strong foundations in scientific knowledge, practices and values in students.

The revised and expanded science curriculum framework encompasses the direction of science education in Singapore and ensures that students are given a solid foundation for life, learning, citizenship and work in science.

The Center’s “Science for Life and Society” reflects the essence of the goals of science education. It is worth noting that students’ skills such as creative problem solving, decision-making, and investigation are further developed.

Practices of Science – Practice in Natural Sciences. Practices consist of three components:

- (1) Demonstrating Ways of Thinking and Acting in Science (WOTD);
- (2) Understanding the Nature of Scientific Knowledge (NOS);
- (3) Connecting Science, Technology, Society, and the Environment (STSE).

The above components represent the set of established procedures and processes related to scientific research, what scientific knowledge is and how it is formed and established, and how science is used in society. Practices serve to emphasize that science is more than the acquisition of knowledge; it is a way of thinking and acting. It is important to understand that the three components, representing the cognitive, epistemic, and social aspects of practice, are closely related to each other.

Singapore's teaching method:

-Singapore has a clearly written curriculum and guidelines for all grades, which are applied at every level of the education system and in every subject

- Teaching is sequential, largely practice-oriented and pragmatic, based on a mixture of Eastern and Western teaching traditions.

- Singapore has established a centralized education system (although other countries have recently been moving towards decentralization), has implemented a system that is well integrated with other government institutions, and has implemented a consistent and well-funded process.

- Teachers adhere to authoritarian forms of interaction with students, which are based on unspoken rules in the classroom. "The teacher speaks and the children listen", there is a strict hierarchy and bureaucracy in schools, grades are important, knowledge is practical, and the teacher is responsible in the classroom. This unique combination of historical experience, requirements and instructions, and cultural aspects has led to an extremely effective system of state education.

- At the same time, the system is flexible and managed by experienced specialists. The Singaporean education system is based on national standards, which determine the requirements that each school graduate must meet

- the student's readiness is checked by final exams.

- A Singaporean teacher is responsible for the results of his students, which encourages teachers to strictly follow the instructions and "coach" children in preparing for tests.

Components of Science Practice

The 3 components of science practice include:

- 1) Demonstrate ways of thinking and learning about science;
- 2) Understand the nature of scientific knowledge;
- 3) Connect science to technology, society, and the environment.

All 3 components are important in developing scientific literacy related to knowledge, context, and the real world.

Practices. Teachers are encouraged to regularly engage students in science practice and help them understand how scientific knowledge develops through inquiry. One component of science practice is ways of thinking and doing. It helps students learn by asking questions and involves a variety of skills and processes.

Results and discussion. There is no clear order of priority among ways of thinking and doing. For example, questions may arise during the process of asking questions and identifying problems when analyzing and interpreting data or conducting experiments. Similarly, the skill of creating opportunities can be used when students are engaged in asking questions and identifying problems, or when creating a plan for explanation and designing solutions.

Developing process skills in the context of practical work in natural sciences

Processes

- Problem solving through innovative thinking
- Decision making
- Research.

Natural sciences study the nature that surrounds us, that is, living and non-living objects and natural phenomena. They are the objects of research of natural sciences. The object of research answers the question “What do you want to study?”

Skills

- Observation
- Comparison
- Classification
- Use of devices and equipment
- Communication
- Conclusion
- Formulation of hypotheses
- Prediction
- Analysis
- Creation of opportunities
- Evaluation

The Singaporean approach to science education is known for its effective and innovative methods in teaching science. The main goal of this approach is to develop students' deep understanding, scientific thinking and problem-solving skills. The following main principles and methods are used in teaching science in the Singaporean education system:

1. Constructive approach

The teaching process in the Singaporean education system is constructive, encouraging students to actively participate, think independently and apply their knowledge in practice. Students are allowed to explore topics on their own, identify variables and conduct experiments.

Methods:

• **Inquiry-based learning:** Guides students to discover new knowledge through experiments. They ask questions, conduct experiments and develop their own understanding based on the results. Information technology can be used to conduct experiments in this process.

- **Problem-based learning:** Students are encouraged to solve real-life problems, such as environmental issues or issues related to technology.

2. Integration of mathematics and science

In Singapore, special attention is paid to connecting science lessons with mathematics and scientific thinking. Students learn to think scientifically, analyze, and use mathematical models.

Methods:

- **Modeling:** Students learn to describe scientific processes, such as chemical or physical phenomena, using mathematical models. This method allows students to better understand concepts and apply a scientific approach to them.

- **Data analysis:** Students conduct experiments, analyze the results, and analyze data using statistical methods.

3. Deep learning

Another important aspect of the Singapore education system is deep learning. This approach allows students to not only memorize knowledge, but also apply it in practice, analyze it, and use it in new situations. It also encourages students to find solutions to given problems through practice.

Methods:

- **Socratic questioning:** The teacher encourages students to think, explain their knowledge, and form new concepts by asking deep questions and challenging problems.

- **Conceptual understanding understanding):** Students try to connect topics, deepen their understanding of concepts, and understand the relationships between them. For example, when studying the concepts of photosynthesis or mechanical energy, they connect them together.

4. Interactivity and collaboration in education

The Singapore education system encourages students to work together. During the learning process, students improve their scientific thinking skills by dividing into groups and working together.

Methods:

- **Group work:** Students divide into groups and conduct experiments, exchange ideas, and enrich each other's knowledge.

- **Peer learning:** Students strengthen their knowledge by helping each other and sharing their understanding.

5. Constructive assessment and teaching Students' engagement and learning in science education in Singapore is constantly assessed. The assessment process is aimed at developing students' deep understanding and scientific skills.

Methods:

- **Formative assessment:** Regularly assessing students' progress, providing them with feedback and providing necessary support.

- **Summative assessment:** Students' final level of knowledge is determined through larger assessments (such as tests and projects). These assessments show the students' learning process.

6. Use of innovative technologies

The active use of modern technologies is also important in teaching science in Singapore. Students learn through simulation of scientific processes, interactive lessons and the use of digital tools. Special attention is paid to learning physics knowledge through virtual laboratories, various programs and applications.

Methods:

- **Virtual lab:** Provides students with the opportunity to conduct various scientific experiments on virtual platforms. For example, virtual laboratories are convenient and effective in the departments of optics and quantum mechanics and astronomy.

- **Interactive simulations:** In physics, chemistry and biology classes, students conduct experiments online using interactive simulations.

Advantages of using the Singapore educational approach:

1. **Deep knowledge:** Forms solid and deep knowledge in students, increases the ability to analyze and use knowledge.

2. **Active learning:** Students learn to think independently by being active in classes.

3. **Applying new knowledge in practice:** Teaches students to apply the scientific approach in everyday life.

4. **Innovative educational tools:** Students develop their knowledge on various platforms by using modern technologies.

Conclusion. The Singaporean approach to education encourages students to think scientifically and independently in teaching natural sciences. This approach provides students with a deep understanding of science and practical skills. Therefore, using this educational system makes science more understandable, interesting and certainly useful for every student. It is clear that today, every teacher will be able to deeply understand and use the capabilities of this educational system, which will bring the education and upbringing process in our dear Uzbekistan to greater heights.

REFERENCES

1. Malikova Muhabbat, Sayfullaeva G. I MODERN FORMS OF ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT WORK OF STUDENTS AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM// SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 3 ISSUE 1 JANUARY 2024 UIF-2022: 8.2| ISSN: 2181-3337| SCIENTISTS
2. Rashidova Nilufar, Sayfullayeva G. I Achieving Transparency in Education// Open Herald: Periodical of Methodical Research Volume 1, Issue 7, November, 2023 ISSN (E): 2810-6385 Website: <https://academiaone.org/index.php/6>
3. Malikova Muhabbat, Bozorova Aziza, Sayfullayeva G. I. Relevance of Independent Educational Activities of Students in the Credit–Modular Education System// Open Academia: Journal of Scholarly Research, 1(8), 40–42. Retrieved from <https://academiaone.org/index.php/4/article/view/297>
4. G.I.Sayfullayeva, H.R.Shodiyev Advantages of teaching subjects in the credit-modular education system based on an integrated approach// Academic Research in Educational Sciences Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal September, Volume 3 | Issue 9 | 2022
5. G.I.Sayfullayeva, I.R.Kamolov, O'.K.Sunnatova, Sh.G'.Khaitova, O.Avezmuratov Information technologies in teaching astronomy. Textbook. Bukhara 2024
6. I.R. Kamolov, B.F.Izbosarov, A.R.Sattorov, G.I.Sayfullayeva, Sh.G'.Khaitova, M.K.Abdulvalayeva Astronomical Data On The Energy Power Of The Sun And Prospects For Using It// Educational Administration: Theory and Practice 2024, 30(6), 2093-2098 ISSN: 2148-2403 <https://kuey.net/>